

Etiological Spectrum of Patients Undergoing Surgery for Intestinal Obstruction

Rajkamal Kanojiya¹, Dhruv Sharma², Rajat Goyal³, Aman Purohit⁴^{1,2,3,4}Department of General Surgery, Mahatma Gandhi Hospital, Jaipur

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Dhruv Sharma

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** Even with advancements in surgical techniques and a better understanding of gastrointestinal physiology, intestinal obstruction remains a frequent and challenging issue for surgeons.**Objective:** This study aims to analyze the epidemiology, frequency, treatment methods, and outcomes associated with intestinal obstruction.**Materials and Methods:** This research involved 200 patients diagnosed with small intestine and colon disorders who received treatment over a period exceeding one year at Mahatma Gandhi Medical College, Jaipur. Diagnosis was based on comprehensive patient history, clinical evaluation, radiological imaging (primarily abdominal), and histopathological examination. Advanced imaging techniques like contrast-enhanced studies and tomography were used selectively. Exclusion criteria included patients with intestinal and anorectal malformations.**Results:** Colon cancer was identified in 6.88% of admissions. Patient ages ranged from 10 days to 82 years, with the highest incidence observed in individuals aged 25-60 years (30.81%). Men were more frequently affected than women. Mild abdominal pain was reported in 80% of cases, with severe pain in 20%. Adhesions were the most common cause of intestinal obstruction (40%), followed by unspecified causes (14%), hernias (9%), and bolus obstruction (7%).**Conclusion:** Adhesions are the predominant cause of intestinal obstruction, often resulting in significant abdominal discomfort. Treatment should be tailored to individual patient needs, with conservative management considered before resorting to surgical intervention.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Both small and large intestines are susceptible to a variety of conditions, with gastrointestinal infections representing approximately 25% of emergency department visits for abdominal pain. The large intestine consists of the small and large intestines, with common obstruction causes including adhesions and tumors. Adhesions, particularly those from prior abdominal surgeries, are responsible for about 65% of small bowel obstructions. Less common complications include intussusception, volvulus, gallstones, and foreign bodies. Diagnosis involves evaluating symptoms, radiography, blood tests, and initial metabolic assessments. Radiological imaging is effective in diagnosing up to 70% of gastric ulcers. Management focuses on relieving the obstruction and may include intravenous fluid therapy and medication. Without proper management, complications such as vascular involvement may arise, necessitating histopathological examination of resected tissues.

Materials and Methods

This study involved 200 patients with small and large bowel issues who were treated for over a year at Mahatma Gandhi Medical College, Jaipur. Excluded were those with anorectal malformations.

Diagnoses were made through comprehensive examination, radiography (X-ray FPA), and histopathological analysis. Additional imaging, such as contrast-enhanced computed tomography, was performed when necessary.

Initial treatment included intravenous fluids, nasogastric suction, and antibiotics, with surgical intervention required for complications.

Surgical approaches varied based on intraoperative findings, with interventions including adhesiolysis, resection, and stoma formation. Postoperative care involved managing oral intake and intravenous fluids based on obstruction etiology and surgical type. Antibiotics were administered, and measures were taken to prevent respiratory and venous complications.

Results

During the study period, 1200 patients were admitted, with 200 (16.66%) presenting with gastrointestinal issues. Ages ranged from 10 days to 80 years, with peak incidences in the 20-40 and 55-65 age groups.

The average age was 34.2 years, with 122 male and 78 female patients. Common symptoms included abdominal pain (80%), vomiting (73%), bloating (71%), and constipation (64%). The predominant cause of obstruction was postoperative adhesions

(42.83%), followed by nonspecific causes (14.71%). Most nonspecific cases involved elderly patients with no history of prior surgery. The average hospital stay was 2.5 days, with about 30% of patients experiencing recurrence. Surgical treatment was most common for adhesions, with procedures including adhesiolysis, resections, and ileostomy. Postoperative complications occurred in 34.74% of cases, with a mortality rate of 4.24%, including both preoperative and postoperative deaths. The average length of stay was 8.6 days for all cases and 3.2 days for those who died.

Table 1: Treatment of patients with subacute intestinal obstruction

Etiology (n)	Management		P value
	Conservative n (%)	Surgical n (%)	
Neoplastic (76)	26(34.2)	50(65.8)	0.02
Tubercular (64)	47(73.43)	17(26.56)	0.04
Stricture with nonspecific histology (30)	2(6.66)	28(93.33)	0.001
Post-surgical adhesions (23)	13(56.52)	10(43.47)	0.76
Crohn's disease (6)	4(66.66)	2(33.33)	0.32
Others (25)	16(64)	9(36)	0.07

Discussion

Acute intestinal obstruction is a serious condition requiring prompt surgical intervention. Recent studies indicate that adhesive obstructions have become more common than hernias.

In this study, 200 cases of intestinal obstruction were analyzed, showing a 5.77% incidence. The age range was broad, with a mean of 30.2 years, and males were more frequently affected.

Adhesive obstruction was the leading cause, similar to findings by other researchers. While hernias are a more common cause in developed countries, they were the third most common cause in this study. Mortality rates were lower compared to some studies but slightly higher than others.

Conclusion

The study confirms that adhesions are the leading cause of intestinal obstruction at our institution. Minimizing adhesion formation during surgery and ensuring thorough radiological and pathological evaluations for patients with colon symptoms are crucial. Attention should also be given to potential late complications such as gastrointestinal issues and chronic pain.

References

1. Irvin TT. Abdominal pain: A surgical audit of 1190 emergency admissions. *Br J Surg.* 1989; 76:1121-5.
2. Shelton BK. Intestinal obstruction. *AACN Clin Issues.* 1999; 10:478-91.
3. Jackson PG, Raiji MT. Evaluation and management of intestinal obstruction. *Am Fam Physician.* 2011; 83:159-65.
4. Maglinte DD, Heitkamp DE, Howard TJ, Kelvin FM, Lappas JC. *Radiol Clin North Am.* 2003; 41:263-83, vi.
5. Lappas JC, Reyes BL, Maglinte DD. Abdominal radiography findings in small-bowel obstruction: Relevance to triage for additional diagnostic imaging. *Am J Roentgenol.* 2001; 176:167-74.
6. Fevang BT, Jensen D, Svanes K, Viste A. Early operation or conservative management of patients with small bowel obstruction? *Eur J Surg.* 2002; 168:475-81.
7. McEntee G, Pender D, Mulvin D, McCullough M, Naeeder S, Farah S, et al. Current spectrum of intestinal obstruction. *Br J Surg.* 1987; 74:976-80.
8. Madziga AG, Nuhu AI. Causes and treatment outcome of mechanical bowel obstruction in north eastern Nigeria. *West Afr J Med.* 2008; 27:101-5.